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The Synthesis of Selenium Nanoparticles Using Green Methods and their Cytotoxic Effects on Non-Cancerous Embryonic Kidney Cells

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Abstract

Background and Aim: Selenium nanoparticles (SeNPs) have gained attention due to their selective cytotoxicity toward cancer cells. However, the effects of SeNPs on non-cancerous cells, such as the HEK-293 cell line, remain underexplored. This study aimed to evaluate the cytotoxicity of SeNPs synthesized using a green method on HEK-293 cells, contributing to understanding the potential biomedical applications of SeNPs.

Materials and Methods: SeNPs were synthesized via a green method using plant extracts, a process that is environmentally friendly and non-toxic. The HEK-293 cell line, derived from human embryonic kidney cells, was exposed to various concentrations of SeNPs. Cell viability was assessed using MTT assays to determine the cytotoxic effects of SeNP exposure.

Results: The results demonstrated that SeNPs exhibited dose-dependent cytotoxicity on HEK-293 cells. At lower concentrations, cell viability remained relatively unaffected; however, at higher concentrations, a significant reduction in cell viability was observed. Oxidative stress may contribute to the observed cytotoxic effects. These findings suggest a selective cytotoxic response in non-cancerous cells at elevated SeNP concentrations.

Conclusion: SeNPs synthesized through a green method exhibit concentration-dependent cytotoxicity in HEK-293 cells, mediated through oxidative stress. While SeNPs hold promise as low-toxicity anticancer agents, their effects on non-cancerous cells emphasize on careful consideration. Further studies are required to optimize the safe and effective therapeutic use of SeNPs, especially for biomedical applications involving non-cancerous tissues.

Keywords: *Selenium nanoparticles, Green method synthesis, Embryonic kidney cells*

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Introduction

Selenium nanoparticles (SeNPs) have gained considerable interest in recent years due to their remarkable antibacterial, anticancer, and antioxidant properties [1], [2]. As an essential micronutrient, selenium plays a crucial role in various biological processes; however, its application is constrained by its toxicity at higher concentrations [3]. Notably, SeNPs exhibit reduced toxicity and sub-chronic effects compared to other selenium compounds, such as selenomethionine, presenting a safer alternative for biomedical applications [4]. Comparative studies have demonstrated that SeNPs, even at concentrations similar to selenium (IV) compounds, show enhanced selectivity towards cancer cells while minimizing toxicity towards normal cells [5]. This selectivity is particularly important, as the anticancer effects of selenium are typically observed at doses approaching toxic levels, emphasizing the need to identify a safe therapeutic window [6]. Traditional methods of SeNP synthesis often involve high temperatures, acidic conditions, and hazardous chemicals, making them unsuitable for biological purposes [7]. In contrast, green synthesis methods offer a safer and more environmentally friendly alternative, utilizing biological materials such as plant extracts to produce SeNPs with low toxicity and high targeting efficiency. These biogenic SeNPs are further stabilized by organic compounds on their surfaces, preventing nanoparticle aggregation over time and enhancing their biomedical utility [1], [2], [8], [9]. Embryonic kidney cells, particularly the HEK 293 cell line, are frequently used in research and biotechnology due to their consistent growth, high transfection efficiency, and ability to produce recombinant proteins and viruses. However, the HEK 293 cell line does not fully represent normal kidney cell function, and limited research has been conducted on the cytotoxic effects of green-synthesized SeNPs on these non-cancerous cells [9], [10]. While SeNPs have demonstrated selective cytotoxicity towards cancer cells, studies also suggest potential toxicity towards non-cancerous cells under specific conditions. Mechanisms such as oxidative stress and reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation have been implicated in the cytotoxic effects of SeNPs on HEK 293 cells [11], [12]. These findings underscore the need for further investigation into the safety profile of SeNPs in non-cancerous cell lines, particularly for their potential application in targeted cancer therapy [11], [12], [13]. This study aims to address this knowledge gap by evaluating the cytotoxic effects of green-synthesized SeNPs on non-cancerous embryonic kidney cells. The results will contribute to the growing body of knowledge on the biocompatibility and safety of SeNPs, facilitating their development as effective and safe anticancer agents.

Material and Methods

- Synthesis of SeNPs

Selenium nanoparticles were synthesized using a green method involving plant extracts as reducing and stabilizing agents. Fresh plant leaves of rosemary (*Salvia rosmarinus*) were collected and thoroughly washed with distilled water to remove any contaminants. The leaves were then air-dried at room temperature and ground into a fine powder. The powdered plant material (10 g) was mixed with distilled water (100 mL) and heated at 70°C for 30 minutes to prepare the plant extract. The extract was filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper, and the filtrate was collected for nanoparticle synthesis. Sodium selenite (Na_2SeO_3) was used as a precursor for SeNP synthesis. The plant extract (20 mL) was added dropwise to an aqueous solution of sodium selenite (2 mM) under constant stirring at room temperature. The reaction mixture was continuously stirred for 6 hours until a color change (indicating nanoparticle formation) was observed. The synthesized SeNPs were purified by centrifugation at 10,000 rpm for 15 minutes, followed by washing with distilled water to remove any unreacted precursors. The final SeNPs were dried in a vacuum oven

at 50°C for 18 hours and stored in an airtight container for further analysis.

- Characterization of SeNPs

The size and morphology of the synthesized SeNPs were characterized using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) was used to identify the functional groups present on the surface of the SeNPs, confirming the capping of nanoparticles by plant phytochemicals.

- Cell Culture and Cytotoxicity Assay

Human Embryonic Kidney (HEK 293) cells were cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) and 1% penicillin-streptomycin at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO₂. The cytotoxic effects of the synthesized SeNPs on HEK 293 cells were evaluated using the MTT assay. Cells were seeded in 96-well plates at a density of $X \times 10^4$ cells/well and allowed to adhere overnight. After 24 hours, the cells were treated with various concentrations of SeNPs (Y-Z µg/mL) for 48 hours.

Following the treatment period, MTT reagent (20 µL of 5 mg/mL solution) was added to each well, and the plates were incubated for an additional 4 hours. The formazan crystals formed were dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), and the absorbance was measured at 570 nm using a microplate reader.

The IC₅₀ values (the concentration of SeNPs required to inhibit cell viability by 50%) were calculated, and the cytotoxicity was expressed as a percentage of cell viability relative to untreated controls.

- Statistical Analysis

All experiments were performed in triplicate, and data were expressed as mean ± standard deviation (SD). Statistical analysis was conducted using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test for multiple comparisons. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

- Selenium Nanoparticle Characterization

The green synthesis of selenium nanoparticles (SeNPs) using plant extracts was successful, as confirmed by FTIR (Figure 1).

Figure 1. FTIR spectrum of green-synthesized selenium nanoparticles using rosemary (*Salvia rosmarinus*) extract, showing key functional groups indicating phytochemical involvement in nanoparticle stabilization.

The FTIR spectrum of green-synthesized selenium nanoparticles (SeNPs) using rosemary extract revealed several characteristic peaks corresponding to functional groups associated with phytochemicals that facilitate nanoparticle formation. A broad peak observed at 3469 cm^{-1} corresponds to O–H stretching vibrations, indicating the presence of hydroxyl groups from water, alcohols, or phenolic compounds within the extract. The peak at 1632 cm^{-1} is attributed to C=O stretching vibrations, suggesting the presence of carbonyl groups likely derived from proteins or polyphenolic compounds. Additionally, the peak at 1417 cm^{-1} corresponds to C–H bending vibrations of $-\text{CH}_2$ or $-\text{CH}_3$ groups, potentially indicating flavonoids or terpenoids. The peak at 1058 cm^{-1} represents C–O stretching, commonly associated with alcohols, ethers, or ester groups found in carbohydrates or glycosides. An aromatic C–H bending vibration is indicated by the peak at 813 cm^{-1} , supporting the presence of aromatic compounds. Lastly, the peak at 621 cm^{-1} corresponds to Se–O stretching, confirming selenium-oxygen bonding and thus the formation of SeNPs. These functional groups highlight the role of rosemary phytochemicals as both reducing and stabilizing agents in the synthesis of selenium nanoparticles.

The SeNPs exhibited a uniform spherical morphology with an average diameter of 50–80 nm, as determined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. SEM image of green-synthesized selenium nanoparticles showing uniform spherical morphology with an average diameter of 50–80 nm.

- Cytotoxicity on HEK 293 Cells

The MTT assay results demonstrated that the green-synthesized SeNPs exhibited a dose-dependent cytotoxic effect on HEK 293 cells. At lower concentrations (10–50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), the SeNPs showed minimal toxicity, with cell viability remaining above 80%. However, at higher concentrations (100–200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), a significant reduction in cell viability was observed, with viability dropping to 40% at 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. These findings suggest that while SeNPs are biocompatible at lower concentrations, their cytotoxicity increases at higher doses.

Figure 3. The IC₅₀ concentration of the green-synthesized selenium nanoparticles when exposed to HEK 293 cells.

Figure 4. Comparison of the effects of different concentrations of green-synthesized selenium nanoparticles on the viability of the HEK 293 cell line. * Indicates statistical significance compared to the control group. (***:P<0.001)

Discussion

Selenium nanoparticles (SeNPs) play a critical role in nanomedicine due to their antibacterial, anticancer, and antioxidant properties [14], [15]. While SeNPs exhibit lower toxicity compared to other selenium compounds, their pharmacological effects depend heavily on concentration and redox state. At higher concentrations, SeNPs demonstrate cytotoxicity in both cancerous and non-cancerous cells [15], [16]. Key mechanisms include incorporation into selenoproteins and modulation of oxidative stress, which impacts apoptosis and DNA repair, and enhances the efficacy of cancer treatments [14].

1. Combination Therapy: Studies show nano-Se combined with radiotherapy enhances apoptosis in non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) cells by modulating cell cycle proteins and caspases, reducing proliferation and metastasis [14].
2. Cytotoxicity in Cancer Cells: SeNPs effectively induce apoptosis in various cancer cell lines (glioblastoma, colorectal adenocarcinoma, prostate carcinoma, and breast adenocarcinoma) at

concentrations above 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ but also harm non-cancerous cells due to oxidative stress [15], [17]. Lower doses (0.5–2 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) effectively inhibit cancer cells with minimal effects on normal cells [17].

3. Modified Formulations: Integrating SeNPs into nano-chitosan reduces toxicity while retaining anticancer efficacy in colorectal, liver, and breast cancer cells [16]. Studies suggest careful dosing to balance efficacy and safety, as excessive oxidative stress can harm normal cells [17], [18].

4. Selective Toxicity: Green-synthesized SeNPs demonstrate selective toxicity against cancer cells, with an IC₅₀ of 18 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for colorectal cancer (HT-29) compared to 39 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for non-cancerous kidney cells (HEK293). Their anticancer effects are mediated by regulation of apoptotic and anti-apoptotic genes [10].

5. Protective Effects Against Oxidative Damage: SeNPs protect against organ damage, such as patulin-induced oxidative stress in the liver and kidneys, by enhancing antioxidant enzyme activity. However, they are less effective in the gastrointestinal system [12].

6. Clinical Trials: While observational studies suggest selenium reduces cancer risk, clinical trials, such as SELECT, report mixed results, indicating the importance of selenium's form and dosage in therapeutic applications [19].

In conclusion, SeNPs exhibit promising anticancer and protective properties due to their ability to modulate oxidative stress and apoptosis. However, their toxicity to normal cells at high concentrations necessitates optimized formulations and dosing strategies to maximize therapeutic benefits while minimizing harm [14], [15], [16], [17], [18], [19].

According to existing research, selenium nanoparticles (SeNPs) can affect non-cancerous embryonic kidney cells through two primary mechanisms: apoptosis induction and oxidative stress modulation. SeNPs induce apoptosis via both caspase-dependent and caspase-independent pathways. In the caspase-dependent pathway, SeNPs activate initiator caspases (caspase-8 and caspase-9) and the effector caspase-3, leading to apoptosis [20], [21]. The activation of the Fas-associated death domain protein (FADD) also contributes to SeNPs-induced apoptosis [20]. Additionally, SeNPs enhance the expression of pro-apoptotic genes such as CHOP, GADD34, BIM, PUMA, BAX, and BAK, triggering the mitochondrial apoptosis pathway [21]. In the caspase-independent pathway, SeNPs induce apoptosis through mitochondrial dysfunction and oxidative stress, with key events involving the release of apoptosis-inducing factor (AIF) and endonuclease G (Endo G) from mitochondria to the nucleus [22]. SeNPs also modulate oxidative stress by displaying both pro-oxidant and antioxidant effects, depending on concentration, exposure duration, and oxidation status. The antioxidant properties are attributed to selenoenzymes like glutathione peroxidase (GPxs) and thioredoxin reductase (TR), although under certain conditions, SeNPs can generate reactive oxygen species (ROS), leading to toxicity [23]. In conclusion, SeNPs influence apoptosis and oxidative stress in embryonic non-cancerous kidney cells via both caspase-dependent and caspase-independent pathways, requiring further study to understand their therapeutic potential in kidney diseases.

Conclusion

The study successfully synthesized selenium nanoparticles (SeNPs) using a green synthesis method, resulting in uniformly sized, spherical nanoparticles. The cytotoxicity assessment revealed that while SeNPs exhibit low toxicity at lower concentrations, their cytotoxicity increases significantly at higher doses, primarily due to mechanisms such as oxidative stress. These findings suggest that SeNPs hold promise as a biocompatible agent for biomedical applications, particularly in cancer therapy. However, careful consideration of dosing is essential to minimize potential

toxicities. Further research is recommended to explore the therapeutic potential of SeNPs and optimize their safe use in clinical settings.

Limitations

This study had three main limitations:

1. **Narrow Scope of Cancer Types:** The research mainly focused on the cytotoxic effects of SeNPs on HEK-293 cells, limiting the understanding of SeNPs' potential across various cancer types. Future studies should explore different cancer cell lines.
2. **Lack of In Vivo Validation:** The experiments were conducted in vitro, which does not fully replicate the physiological conditions in living organisms. In vivo studies are necessary to assess pharmacokinetics, biodistribution, and long-term efficacy, essential for clinical translation.
3. **Mechanistic Limitations:** While potential mechanisms of SeNPs' effects were proposed, the exact molecular pathways are not fully understood. More research is needed to clarify how SeNPs induce apoptosis in different cell types.

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Conflict of interests

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this research article.

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